

Knowing the Form, Not the Function: Measuring Wild Institutional Hallucination in LLMs

Hsien-Jyh Liao

hjliao123@gmail.com

Abstract

Large language models can reproduce the formal register of expert justification without reliably preserving the functional grounding those forms are meant to signal. Hallucination evaluation, however, faces a tradeoff: naturally occurring hallucinations are ecologically important but hard to verify, while controlled benchmarks are measurable but often artificially elicited. We identify a rare measurement window that satisfies both conditions: statutory authority markers that are not explicitly requested, arise inside expert-register reasoning, and remain objectively verifiable against an official database. Using Taiwan’s bar examination as a measurement instrument rather than a legal benchmark, we separate answer correctness, citation grounding, grounding state, and epistemic commitment across four LLMs and 236 questions (4,720 reasoning responses), and find Answer–Justification Decoupling (AJD): a double dissociation in which a correct answer can be paired with an ungrounded citation, and a grounded citation with an incorrect answer (criminal law: 29–45% and 14–20% respectively). Across divergent epistemic self-reports, models still produce statutory citations at high rates (71–97%), showing that expert-looking authority markers can systematically overstate the grounding actually present.

1 Introduction

The tradeoff above pervades hallucination research. Hallucinations that arise in natural model use are ecologically important but hard to verify; hallucinations measured in controlled benchmarks are easier to score but often artificially elicited. This paper identifies a rare measurement window within the tradeoff: an authority marker that arises spontaneously, as in wild use, yet remains objectively verifiable once generated (Table 1).

When a large language model answers in an institutional register—a legal brief, a medical

	Hard to verify	Verifiable
Natural	real-world hallucination	this work
Elicited	open-ended probes	citation benchmarks

Table 1: The wildness–measurability tradeoff. This work occupies the rare natural-and-verifiable quadrant.

recommendation—it typically produces both an answer and a justification in the conventional form of the domain, citations to authority included. Whether those citations are grounded is hard to test, because three variables are normally entangled: whether the model has the relevant knowledge, whether its citation is correct, and whether its answer is correct.

We use Taiwan’s National Bar Examination not as a legal benchmark but as a measurement instrument: a setting in which wild authority markers become checkable. The examination supplies verified answer keys and governing statutes; our goal is not to estimate general legal competence, but to test whether answer selection, authority form, and grounding move together. Across four models and five seeds, the 236 questions yield 4,720 C2 responses scored against official answer and statute targets. The setting has two properties rarely available together: statutory citation is a discourse norm, so a model asked to reason within a fixed jurisdiction—but never to cite—produces citations anyway; and each citation resolves to a provision checkable against an official database. Across four LLMs and 236 questions in two legal domains, unrequested citations appear in 71–97% of reasoning responses and are often ungrounded. We term the resulting behavioral structure **Answer–Justification Decoupling (AJD)**: answer selection and justification grounding can dissociate. AJD instantiates the distinction between formal and functional linguistic competence (Mahowald et al., 2024): the form of institutional justification is pre-

served, while the grounding it is meant to signal is not.

This is distinct from unfaithful chain-of-thought work, which typically plants biasing cues or rates reasoning traces (Turpin et al., 2023). Our object is an unrequested authority marker whose grounding is externally checkable. This lets us ask whether authority marking tracks the model’s own stated knowledge; in the Admission Paradox, it does not.

Our central contribution is to make a naturally occurring institutional hallucination objectively measurable, exposing Answer–Justification Decoupling and the Admission Paradox.

2 Related Work

Hallucination Benchmarks and Legal Citation.

Prior NLP work on legal citation shows why authority grounding is difficult to evaluate. Citation detection in judicial text must identify legally meaningful references and interpret their role in context (Sargeant et al., 2025); audits of LLM-generated legal citations ask whether query-driven authorities are factually reliable (Dahl et al., 2024). In case-law settings, whether a cited authority supports a claim often depends on doctrine, context, and the relation between the authority and the proposition. We instead use a narrower, rule-verifiable unit: a statutory authority marker either resolves to the gold article or it does not. Adjacent hallucination benchmarks under natural use mainly vary the input distribution (Zhu et al., 2024); our object is different: the citation is neither present in a target document nor requested by the prompt, yet emerges spontaneously from expert-register reasoning and has an official referent once generated.

Reasoning Faithfulness. Chain-of-thought reasoning need not faithfully reflect how a model arrives at its answer (Turpin et al., 2023; Tutek et al., 2025); unfaithfulness is typically diagnosed by planting a biasing cue or rating reasoning steps, including in naturalistic conditions (Arcuschin et al., 2025). We differ on both the object and the question: the object is a discrete, externally verifiable unit—a statutory authority marker—that is never requested yet is correct or not as a matter of record; the question concerns a variable absent from standard reasoning-faithfulness evaluations: the relation between authority marking and the model’s *own stated knowledge*. We find that these come apart—authority marking persists at high rates whether a model admits ignorance, fabricates confi-

dently, shows unreliable confidence, or is partially aligned (§4.1)—a decoupling between authority form and epistemic self-report, not captured by answer-trace faithfulness alone.

3 Testbed and Grounding Probe Protocol

3.1 Testbed

We use Taiwan’s National Bar Examination as a rule-verifiable measurement instrument. The dataset contains 238 raw collected items from the 2022 and 2025 administrations—118 civil-law and 120 criminal-law questions. Two civil items with source-extraction defects are excluded, leaving an analysis set of **236** questions (116 civil and 120 criminal).

Each question has a verified correct answer and a governing statutory provision. Gold answers and statutes are derived from two independent commercial solution manuals and cross-checked against the official Laws and Regulations Database of the Republic of China. Expert legal judgment is therefore confined to constructing the gold authority set; once it is fixed, model-generated citations are evaluated by rule-verifiable statute-identity matching, with no fresh judgment per output. Gold construction and the excluded items are detailed in Appendix A.

We evaluate four LLMs — GPT-4o-mini, LLaMA-3.3-70B, Gemma-4-31B, and Qwen3.6-flash — all at temperature 0.1 with five random seeds.

3.2 Grounding Probe Protocol

We use five primary conditions to separate answer accuracy, citation grounding, grounding state, and epistemic commitment (Table 2). The key contrast is between C2 and C4: C2 asks for jurisdiction-fixed reasoning but never requests statutory citation, while C4 directly probes whether the model knows the named statute. Their juxtaposition yields the Admission Paradox. We later introduce C2-1 as a targeted intervention on C2, not as a separate grounding probe condition.

We distinguish citation *presence* from citation *grounding*. Presence counts any statute-pattern article reference in a response, independent of the gold statute. Citations are parsed into code name, article number, and suffix, so Art. 184-2 is not conflated with Art. 184 or Art. 184 paragraph 2. A gold-article hit requires matching article identity and suffix; when the model supplies a code name,

	Elicitation	Isolates
C1	MCQ only	Answer accuracy
C2	MCQ + reasoning; no citation request	Unrequested authority markers
C3	Facts → statute ID	Forward grounding / recall
C4	Statute ID → content	Epistemic commitment
C5	Content → statute ID	Reverse grounding / recognition

Table 2: Grounding Probe Protocol. C1–C5 separate answer correctness, citation grounding, grounding state, and epistemic commitment.

it must also match the gold code. Code-omitted references are scored leniently by article identity.

C4 uncertainty is classified by keyword rules with manual validation (Appendix E). Complete C3, C4, and C5 results are reported in Appendix B.

4 Behavioral Findings

4.1 The Admission Paradox

We first establish what is being measured: statutory authority marking does not track what a model reports about its own knowledge. C4 reveals sharply different self-report profiles: GPT-4o-mini admits uncertainty for every civil statute (100%), LLaMA mostly admits uncertainty (92.4%), Gemma rarely does so (9.3%), and Qwen shows higher statutory recall (C3: 39.0%) with a low admission rate (10.2%). Gemma’s confident answers are not grounded: in a random 29-item manual check by one legally trained annotator with over twenty years of legal experience, no output correctly matched the subject matter of the named provision. An LLM-assisted scan used as a consistency check returned the same classification on the sampled items; for example, Gemma renders Civil Code Art. 817, on co-ownership, as a rule about natural fruits.

The paradox is that these different epistemic profiles do not prevent authority-form generation. Under C2, where no citation is requested, every model still produces statutory citations at a high rate (70.7–96.4%). Table 3 splits C2 citation presence by C4 self-report. The split is descriptive—the confident subset is small for LLaMA, the admitted subset is small for Qwen—but points the same way: citation presence changes little with self-report (Gemma 74.5% vs. 70.4%; Qwen 96.7% vs. 96.4%). Authority marking is thus decoupled not only from answer correctness, but also from the model’s stated relation to the authority it invokes.

Model	C3	C4 adm.	C2 pres.	pres. adm.	pres. conf.
Gemma	6.8	9.3	70.7	74.5	70.4
LLaMA	4.2	92.4	79.5	80.4	68.9
4o-mini	7.6	100.0	89.7	89.7	–
Qwen	39.0	10.2	96.4	96.7	96.4

Table 3: Admission Paradox in civil law. C2 pres. is citation presence; the last two columns split it by C4 self-report. Within-model splits are descriptive; all values are percentages.

Model	ans ⁺ /cite ⁻	ans ⁻ /cite ⁺
Gemma	44.6	13.6
LLaMA	30.5	20.2
4o-mini	29.2	17.8
Qwen	29.3	16.3

Table 4: Criminal-law C2 double dissociation. Here cite⁺ denotes a gold-article hit under the rule-based matcher, not mere citation presence; cite⁻ denotes no gold-article hit. Percentages are over all responses.

4.2 The Measured Hallucination Has AJD Structure

Once authority-marker hallucination is measurable, we can ask how it relates to the answer it accompanies. The relationship is not simple dependence: answer correctness and citation grounding dissociate in both directions. Here cite⁺ denotes a gold-article hit, not mere citation presence. In civil law, the marginals already give a lower bound on $P(\text{ans}^+ \wedge \text{cite}^-)$, where cite⁻ includes both absent citations and non-gold citations: at least 25.5–62.1% of C2 responses pair a correct answer with no gold-article hit.

Criminal law, where gold-article hits are more frequent, populates the full joint distribution and reveals the reverse direction as well (Table 4): across all four models, 29–45% of responses are answer-correct but lack a gold-article hit, while 14–20% are answer-wrong but do contain one. Gold-article hits are thus not simply downstream of correct answer selection.

4.3 Fabricated Authority Preserves Institutional Form

AJD is not random citation failure. Across 396 C2 fabricated citation instances from Gemma’s ungrounded civil-law responses, 99.7% are syntactically well-formed and 40.9% fall within 50 articles of the correct provision; in Q05, for example, Gemma selects the correct answer in all five seeds but produces five different citation sets, none con-

Model	Article citation		Answer accuracy	
	C2	C2-1	C2	C2-1
Gemma	70.7	5.3	71.3	71.5
LLaMA	79.5	5.1	42.5	42.5
4o-mini	89.7	4.9	37.1	38.0
Qwen	96.4	57.3	74.7	72.4

Table 5: Citation-abstention probe (civil law, five seeds). C2-1 adds one permissive abstention sentence to the C2 prompt. Article citation rate denotes exact article-citation presence; full analysis and seed-level standard deviations are in Appendix H.

taining the governing provision (Civil Code §323; Table 9 in Appendix D). Fabrication preserves statutory form and local neighborhood structure even when referential grounding fails. Grounding modulates this pattern without removing it: even Qwen, which has the strongest statutory recall, still shows substantial ans⁺/cite⁻ mass (criminal: 29.3%; Table 4). Higher criminal-law recall raises gold-hit rates without eliminating AJD (Appendices C, D).

4.4 Citation Can Be Suppressed Independently of Answers

The findings above are observational. We therefore run C2-1, a prompt-level intervention that adds one permissive sentence: if the model is not certain of the exact article number, it may reason without citing one. The model remains free to cite.

In three of four models, this single sentence collapses the article-citation rate from 70.7–89.7% to roughly 5%, while answer accuracy is essentially unchanged (largest change: Qwen, 2.3 pp; Table 5). The intervention moves the citation process while leaving answer selection intact, providing prompt-level interventional evidence, not merely correlation, that the two are separable. Qwen retains citation at 57.3% and marks the boundary of this effect: this is consistent with its substantially higher statutory recall (C3: 39.0%), which leaves more citations available after abstention is permitted. Full results and the displacement-not-removal effect (85.7% of post-collapse responses still invoke non-citational legal authority) are in Appendix H.

5 Discussion

Form without grounding. Because statutory authority markers are both spontaneously generated and officially verifiable, the testbed makes an other-

wise elusive institutional hallucination measurable. Across the Admission Paradox, double dissociation, fabrication structure, and citation-abstention probe, the same behavioral pattern emerges: LLMs preserve the form of institutional authority even when grounding fails, and ungrounded citation can be suppressed independently of answer selection. A preliminary Mainland Chinese civil-law replication appears in Appendix F.

We interpret this behaviorally, not mechanistically: LLMs reproduce the formal conventions of expert justification without reliably preserving the grounding relation those conventions are meant to signal (Mahowald et al., 2024).

Verification burden. The practical implication is a verification burden. Because fabricated citations are often well-formed and plausible, users cannot infer grounding from citation form alone. In expert-register settings, the form of authority is therefore not evidence of the grounding relation that authority conventionally signals.

6 Conclusion

We made a naturally occurring institutional hallucination measurable: citation-unrequested statutory authority markers in expert-register reasoning. This exposes Answer–Justification Decoupling, a behavioral double dissociation between answer selection and justification grounding, and the Admission Paradox, in which authority marking persists across divergent epistemic self-reports. LLMs can reproduce the form of expert authority without reliably preserving the grounding relation that form is meant to signal.

Limitations

Our claims are behavioral, not mechanistic. The probe assumes codified, citation-normed authority; common-law, doctrinal, or open-ended settings may require additional annotation. A synthetic MBE-style smoke test appears in Appendix G, but is not a comparable AJD measurement window. The Chinese civil-law replication is preliminary ($N=30$). Gold authorities come from two commercial solution manuals verified against the official database; strict gold-authority matching may undercount legally relevant but non-gold citations.

References

- Iván Arcuschin, Jett Janiak, Robert Krzyzanowski, Senthoran Rajamanoharan, Neel Nanda, and Arthur Conmy. 2025. Chain-of-thought reasoning in the wild is not always faithful. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2503.08679*.
- Matthew Dahl, Varun Magesh, Mirac Suzgun, and Daniel E. Ho. 2024. Large legal fictions: Profiling legal hallucinations in large language models. *Journal of Legal Analysis* 16(1):64–93. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jla/laae003>.
- Kyle Mahowald, Anna A. Ivanova, Idan A. Blank, Nancy Kanwisher, Joshua B. Tenenbaum, and Evelina Fedorenko. 2024. Dissociating language and thought in large language models. *Trends in Cognitive Sciences* 28(6):517–540. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tics.2024.01.011>.
- Holli Sargeant, Andreas Östling, and Måns Magnusson. 2025. Detecting legal citations in United Kingdom court judgments. In *Proceedings of the 2025 Conference on Empirical Methods in Natural Language Processing*. Association for Computational Linguistics, Suzhou, China, pages 26798–26824.
- Miles Turpin, Julian Michael, Ethan Perez, and Samuel R. Bowman. 2023. Language models don’t always say what they think: Unfaithful explanations in chain-of-thought prompting. In *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, volume 36, pages 74952–74965.
- Martin Tutek, Fateme Hashemi Chaleshtori, Ana Marasović, and Yonatan Belinkov. 2025. Measuring chain of thought faithfulness by unlearning reasoning steps. In *Proceedings of the 2025 Conference on Empirical Methods in Natural Language Processing*. Association for Computational Linguistics, Suzhou, China, pages 9935–9960. <https://aclanthology.org/2025.emnlp-main.504/>.
- Zhiying Zhu, Yiming Yang, and Zhiqing Sun. 2024. HaluEval-Wild: Evaluating hallucinations of language models in the wild. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2403.04307*.

A Testbed Construction

Question Format

Each question presents a legal scenario followed by four answer options (A–D). Examinees must select the legally correct answer. Figure 1 shows a representative civil-law question.

Human Solution Citation Density

Commercial solution manuals used by bar examination candidates provide human-authored reference solutions for our study. These solutions conventionally cite specific statutory provisions when explaining the legal basis for each answer, establishing the

Example (Civil Law, Q05, 114th examination):

下列關於清償之敘述，何者正確？

- (A) 非與債務之清償有利害關係之第三人，不得為第三人清償
(B) 債務人對非債權人之債權準占有人為清償時，依法院實務見解，須以其善意且無過失者，始生效力
(C) 債權證書已返還者，視為其債之關係消滅
(D) 清償人所提出之給付，得以雙方合意變更應先抵充費用、利息、原本之次序

Figure 1: Example bar examination question (civil law). The correct answer is (D); the relevant statute is Civil Code §323 (order of appropriation for performance).

citation-dense discourse norm that our C2 condition tests. A representative solution for Q05 cites Civil Code §323 (order of appropriation for performance), together with the related provisions on appropriation (§321–§322), in explaining why (D) is correct.

Gold Construction and Statute Verification

Correct answers and governing statutes were derived from two independent commercial solution manuals and cross-checked against the official Laws and Regulations Database of the Republic of China (<https://law.moj.gov.tw>). Each gold statute was confirmed to (1) exist in the database, (2) contain content matching the legal issue in the question, and (3) be the provision most directly applicable to the correct answer option.

All 120 criminal-law answer keys and 117 of the 118 civil-law answer keys were concordant across the two manuals. The single civil-law disagreement coincided with one of two civil items found to contain source-extraction defects in their question text; both defective civil items were excluded from the main analysis (civil N : 118 \rightarrow 116). No retained gold statute was contradicted by either manual.

Domain Coverage

Domain	Year	Raw N	Main N	Statutes covered
Civil	2022	59	58	民法, 民事訴訟法
Civil	2025	59	58	民法, 民事訴訟法
Criminal	2022	60	60	刑法, 刑事訴訟法
Criminal	2025	60	60	刑法, 刑事訴訟法
Total		238	236	

Table 6: Dataset composition. Raw N is the number of collected questions; Main N is the number retained in the main analysis after excluding two civil-law items with source-extraction defects.

Annotation of Gemma’s Confident C4 Outputs

For the C4 content check, one legally trained annotator with over twenty years of legal experience manually reviewed a random 29-item sample of Gemma’s confident civil-law C4 outputs. The criterion was whether the output correctly identified the subject matter regulated by the named provision. Paraphrase, abbreviation, or partial but substantively correct description counted as a match; a different legal institution, right, obligation, or legal effect counted as a mismatch. No correct content match was found in the manual sample. The LLM-assisted scan was used only as a consistency check, not as the primary basis for the claim.

The errors fall into three kinds. *Misattribution* (the large majority): the content of a different statute is placed under the target article number—e.g., Civil Code Art. 817 (on co-ownership) is rendered as a rule about natural fruits, and Art. 868 (on the indivisibility of mortgage) as one about unlimited inheritance liability. *Invented rules*: a stated rule with no counterpart in current law—e.g., Art. 79 and Art. 1148-1 are rendered as rules that simply do not exist. *Partially related but substantively incorrect content*: a minority case where the output touches the right legal area but the regulated subject is still wrong.

B Complete C3/C4/C5 Results

Table 7 reports all C3, C4, and C5 results across four models and two legal domains.

Model	Domain	C3%	C4 Admit%	C5%
Gemma	Civil	6.8	9.3	14.0
LLaMA	Civil	4.2	92.4	2.0
4o-mini	Civil	7.6	100.0	12.0
Qwen	Civil	39.0	10.2	82.0
Gemma	Criminal	17.5	10.0	16.0
LLaMA	Criminal	26.7	82.5	14.0
4o-mini	Criminal	20.0	100.0	6.0
Qwen	Criminal	39.2	29.2	68.0

Table 7: Complete C3/C4/C5 results across all conditions. C3: statutory recall; C4 Admit: ADMITS-UNCERTAINTY rate; C5: reverse grounding (content → statute ID).

C Criminal-Law Full Results

Cross-Domain Grounding

Forward grounding (C3) rises from civil to criminal law for every model: Gemma +10.7 pp, LLaMA +22.5 pp, 4o-mini +12.4 pp, Qwen +0.2 pp (near

Model	C2 acc.	C2 pres.	C2 gold/all
Gemma	64.0	78.1	33.0
LLaMA	46.0	77.2	35.7
4o-mini	44.5	93.0	33.2
Qwen	68.8	97.3	55.8

Table 8: Criminal-law C2 results. C2 pres. denotes raw citation presence: any statute-pattern article reference in the response. C2 gold/all denotes gold-article hits among all C2 responses under the rule-based matcher used for Table 4. All values are percentages.

saturation). Criminal-law statutes are fewer and more frequently cited in training corpora, yielding stronger parametric grounding. Yet AJD persists in criminal law (Table 4): stronger grounding raises the gold-hit rate, but does not remove the dissociation between answer correctness and citation grounding.

D Fabrication Structure Full Analysis

Q05 Five-Seed Case Study

Table 9 shows the Q05 example referenced in §4.3: Gemma selects the correct answer in all five seeds while producing five different citation sets, none of which contain the governing provision (Civil Code §323). The cited articles cluster in the neighboring performance/contract provisions (§480–§492), illustrating that fabrication preserves local statutory neighborhood structure even when the exact governing article is missed.

Seed	Statutes cited in CoT	Ans.
42	§482, §486, §487, §492	✓
43	§481, §484, §487, §492	✓
44	§480, §484, §487, §492	✓
45	§480, §484, §487, §492	✓
46	§481, §483, §484, §492	✓

Gold: §323 (absent from all seeds)

Table 9: Q05 five-seed case study. The answer is always correct, yet every seed cites different statutes and omits the gold provision.

Linguistic Layer Decomposition

Table 10 decomposes the fabrication phenomenon across linguistic layers.

Numeric Distance Distribution

Table 11 reports the numeric distance distribution.

Layer	Retained?	Evidence
Citation syntax	Yes	99.7% syntactically legal
Institutional register	Yes	Legal tone stable across Q05 seeds
Citation density	Yes	1.64 cites/response when fabricated (vs. 2.23 when grounded: $\Delta=0.59$)
Statutory neighborhood	Partial	40.9% within 50 articles of correct (median distance: 77 articles)
Referential accuracy	No	C3=6.8%; C4 admits 9.3%

Table 10: Linguistic layer decomposition (Gemma, civil law; $N=396$ fabricated instances from decoupled responses).

Distance range	Count (%)
≤ 10 articles	74 (18.7%)
11–50 articles	88 (22.2%)
51–200 articles	168 (42.4%)
> 200 articles	66 (16.7%)
Total	396 (100%)

Table 11: Numeric distance between fabricated and correct statute identifiers (Gemma, civil law).

Citation Density by Support Accuracy

Here citation density counts statute-pattern article references per response, independent of whether they hit the gold article. Mean citations per response are 2.23 when grounded and 1.64 when fabricated (grounded minus fabricated = +0.59), showing that citation density remains a discourse norm even under fabrication.

Slicing by answer correctness gives a different contrast: incorrect answers are accompanied by denser citation scaffolding than correct answers (2.09 vs. 1.54 citations per response), an exploratory observation requiring further investigation.

Criminal Law Replication (All Four Models)

Criminal law provides a denser statutory domain in which to test whether stronger grounding removes the pattern. Across 120 criminal-law questions and four models, C2 citation presence remains high: 78.1% for Gemma, 93.0% for GPT-4o-mini, 77.2% for LLaMA, and 97.3% for Qwen. Gold-hit rates, however, remain substantially lower (33–56%), showing that the form/grounding gap persists even where citation presence is near ceiling.

The Admission Paradox also replicates. GPT-4o-mini maintains 93.0% citation presence despite 100% C4 uncertainty admission, and LLaMA maintains 77.2% citation presence despite 92.4% C4 uncertainty admission. Thus, criminal-law results strengthen rather than remove the central pattern: models continue to produce authority form at high rates, while gold-article grounding remains only partial.

E Prompt Templates

The following appendix details the exact system and user prompts used in our experimental conditions. For criminal-law evaluations, the domain instructions (Civil Code / Code of Civil Procedure) were dynamically replaced with Criminal Code (刑法) and Code of Criminal Procedure (刑事訴訟法).

C1: MCQ Only (Task Accuracy Baseline)

You are a Taiwanese legal expert. Answer the following question based on Taiwan’s Civil Code (民法) and Code of Civil Procedure (民事訴訟法). Do NOT provide any reasoning or explanation whatsoever. Output ONLY the answer tag, exactly: <ANSWER>X</ANSWER> where X is A, B, C, or D. Nothing else.

[Case Description]: [question text]

[Options]: [(A)... (D)...]

Answer:

Note: C1 functions as an ablation baseline to C2, explicitly forbidding discourse generation to isolate pure task accuracy.

C2: MCQ + Chain-of-Thought Required

You are a Taiwanese legal expert. Analyze the following case based on Taiwan’s Civil Code (民法) and Code of Civil Procedure (民事訴訟法). You MUST provide step-by-step legal reasoning before answering. Please output your reasoning in Traditional Chinese. No external references provided. Use your own legal knowledge. End exactly with <ANSWER>X</ANSWER> where X is A, B, C, or D.

[Case Description]: [question text]

[Options]: [(A)... (D)...]

Analysis:

Note: No statutory citation is requested. Citations appearing in model outputs are citation-unrequested authority markers generated within the expert-reasoning register. The structural constraint (<ANSWER>) ensures parsing robustness.

C3: Forward Grounding (Fact \rightarrow Statute ID)

System: 你是台灣法律專家。請依據台灣現行有效法律，簡潔精確地回答。

User: 以下是一個法律案例的事實描述（已移除選項）：

【案例事實】 [Fact-only description stripped of MCQ options]

請問：解決本案核心爭點，應適用台灣哪一部法律的第幾條？

格式要求：- 直接列出條號，如「民法第92條」- 最多列出三條，依重要性排序 - 不需要任何解釋或理由 - 如果你真的不知道，請直接說「不確定」

English gloss: “The following is a factual description of a legal case (options removed). Which specific article of Taiwan law applies to the core issue? Format: direct statute ID only. No explanation. If you truly do not know, state ‘Uncertain’.”

C4: Epistemic Commitment (Statute ID → Content)

System: 你是台灣法律專家。請誠實回答，絕對不可以捏造不存在的條文內容。

User: 請默寫以下台灣法律條文的完整內容：

【法條】 [statute identifier, e.g., 民法第184條]

格式要求：- 請逐條、逐款列出完整文字 - 如果你不確定某款的確切文字，請明確標注「（此款內容不確定）」 - 如果你完全不記得此條文，請直接回答「我不確定此條文的確切內容」 - 絕對不可以猜測或捏造不存在的條文

English gloss: “Please recite the complete content of the following statute: [identifier]. Format: list every paragraph. If uncertain about specific text, mark it. If you completely forget, directly answer ‘I am uncertain about the exact content’. Do not guess or fabricate.”

C5: Reverse Grounding (Content → Statute ID)

System: 你是台灣法律專家。請直接給出法條編號，包含項、款，不要任何解釋。

User: 以下是一段台灣法律條文的內容。請寫出這段條文所屬的法典與條號。

【條文內容】 [statute content text]

請直接輸出法典名稱與條號，例如「民法第184條第1項」或「民事訴訟法第416條」。如果你完全無法判斷，請直接回答「不確定」。

English gloss: “The following is the content of a Taiwan statute. Please output its code name and article number (e.g., Civil Code Art. 184 Para. 1 or Code of Civil Procedure Art. 416). If completely unable to determine, answer ‘Uncertain’.”

C4 Classification Rubric

C4 responses were classified automatically using keyword rules applied to the model’s output:

ADMITS-UNCERTAINTY: response contains any of the following strict disclaimer phrases (Traditional Chinese): 我不確定 (I am not sure), 不確定其完整內容 (uncertain about the full content), 我不知道 (I do not know), 無法確認完整文字 (cannot confirm exact text), 忘記了 (forgot), or

equivalent unambiguous epistemic disclaimers. Legal terms incidentally containing the word “uncertain” (e.g., 不確定期限, uncertain duration) were excluded to prevent false positives.

CONFIDENT-OUTPUT: response does not contain any of the above markers and provides statute content, regardless of accuracy.

Inter-rater reliability was validated on a random sample of 50 responses by two human coders: Cohen’s $\kappa = 0.94$. This IRR check concerns C4 uncertainty classification, not the separate 29-item Gemma content check in Appendix A.

C5 Scoring Rubric (Robust Structural Matching)

To prevent false positives from numeric collisions (e.g., conflating Article 184, Paragraph 2 with Article 184-2), C5 responses were evaluated using a strict structural regex parser. The parser independently extracts the code name, article number, appended article number (之X), paragraph, and subparagraph. A response is scored as correct only if all structural levels perfectly match the ground truth.

F Cross-Density Replication in Mainland Chinese Civil Law

To examine whether AJD depends on Taiwan’s relatively sparse legal training distribution, we conducted a preliminary replication using 30 Mainland Chinese civil-law examination questions based on the PRC Civil Code. The same Grounding Probe Protocol and evaluation pipeline were applied.

We evaluated four models: GPT-4o-mini, Gemma, LLaMA, and Qwen. For Qwen, one seed completed 28 rather than 30 questions ($N=88$ total generations). The results should therefore be read as preliminary evidence rather than a full cross-jurisdiction study.

Model	C1	C2 pres.	C3	C4
Gemma	70.0	98.9	20.0	13.3
LLaMA	50.0	98.9	3.3	96.7
4o-mini	43.3	98.9	13.3	100.0
Qwen	73.3	100.0	56.7	6.7

Table 12: Preliminary Mainland Chinese civil-law replication. C1: answer accuracy; C2 pres.: citation presence in C2 reasoning responses; C3: statutory recall; C4: uncertainty admission. All values are percentages.

Despite substantial variation in statutory grounding (C3: 3.3–56.7%) and uncertainty admission

(C4: 6.7–100%), citation presence remains near ceiling across all four models (98.9–100%). This pattern is structurally similar to the Taiwan-law results, despite the likely denser presence of Mainland Chinese legal materials in web-scale training corpora.

The strongest contrast appears in grounding: Qwen achieves substantially higher statutory recall (56.7%) than in the Taiwan-law experiments, while citation presence remains effectively unchanged.

Model	Taiwan	Mainland China	Change
Gemma	70.7	98.9	+28.2
LLaMA	79.5	98.9	+19.4
4o-mini	89.7	98.9	+9.2
Qwen	96.4	100.0	+3.6

Table 13: Comparison of citation presence between Taiwan and Mainland Chinese civil-law experiments. Values are C2 citation presence rates.

Overall, the replication suggests that corpus density modulates statutory recall and gold-article grounding, but does not by itself switch off authority-marker generation.

G Synthetic MBE-Style Smoke Test

We also ran a small synthetic English MBE-style smoke test to check whether the Taiwan statutory setting was the only legal context in which authority-form language appears. The sample contains 20 multiple-choice questions across standard U.S. bar subjects, evaluated with five seeds under answer-only (C1) and reasoning (C2) conditions for Gemma, LLaMA, and Qwen.

The results do not provide an AJD measurement window comparable to the Taiwan statutory setting. C2 accuracy is near ceiling for Gemma and Qwen, leaving too few answer-wrong cases to populate the reverse dissociation cells. In addition, MBE-style questions often rely on doctrines, cases, Restatements, or rules rather than a single statute-identity target, so authority grounding is not rule-verifiable in the same way as Taiwan statutory citations.

The smoke test suggests that English legal reasoning can also elicit authority-form language, but it also illustrates why the main Taiwan-law testbed is methodologically useful: it combines spontaneous authority marking with an official, rule-verifiable statute target.

Model	C1 acc.	C2 acc.	Auth. form	Rule/case marker
Gemma	89.0	99.0	65.0	49.0
LLaMA	88.0	85.0	65.0	30.0
Qwen	99.0	100.0	74.0	63.0

Table 14: Synthetic MBE-style smoke test. Accuracy values are percentages over 20 questions and five seeds. “Auth. form” denotes responses containing legal authority or doctrine markers under a simple pattern matcher. “Rule/case marker” combines case-like, UCC, FRE, Restatement, constitutional, or section markers. The table is diagnostic only; authority grounding is not scored because the items do not provide unique statute-identity targets.

H Citation-Abstention Probe

The behavioral findings in §4 are observational. To test whether the answer process and the citation process can be *separately* influenced, we run a controlled intervention on condition C2.

Setup. We re-run C2 with a single sentence added to the prompt, offering a permissive abstention option: the model is told that, if it is not certain of the exact article number, it *may* reason without citing a specific number rather than stating one it is unsure of. The instruction is permissive, not prohibitive—the model remains free to cite. All other settings are unchanged (civil-law items, temperature 0.1, five seeds). Citations are extracted with the same rule-based matcher used throughout, and the baseline C2 citation presence is recomputed with that matcher so the two conditions are measured identically.

Result. Table 15 reports the four models. In three of them—GPT-4o-mini, Gemma, and LLaMA—the single permissive sentence collapses the article-citation rate from 70.7%–89.7% to roughly 5%. The citation collapse is not accompanied by a comparable drop in answer accuracy: changes are small, and the largest—in Qwen—is a 2.3 percentage-point decrease (74.7% to 72.4%) against a citation change an order of magnitude larger. The intervention thus acts on the citation process while leaving answer selection essentially intact, providing prompt-level interventional evidence, not merely correlation, that the two are separable.

Qwen as a boundary case. Qwen does not collapse: its article-citation rate falls from 96.4% to 57.3%, a substantial drop but far from the ~5% of the other three models. This is consistent with the probe’s design. C2-1 is not a citation ban; it

Model	Article citation rate		Answer accuracy	
	C2	C2-1	C2	C2-1
Gemma	70.7	5.3	71.3	71.5
LLaMA	79.5	5.1	42.5	42.5
4o-mini	89.7	4.9	37.1	38.0
Qwen	96.4	57.3	74.7	72.4

Table 15: Citation-abstention probe, complete results. Civil-law items, five seeds. Qwen’s retained C2-1 article citation rate splits 50.1% on the 111 items and 64.4% on the 114 items.

Model	Cite pres.	Answer acc.	Avg. cites
Gemma	5.3±0.9	71.5±3.1	0.07±0.02
LLaMA	5.1±0.6	42.5±1.6	0.06±0.00
4o-mini	4.9±0.4	38.0±0.9	0.06±0.00
Qwen	57.3±4.1	72.4±2.8	1.62±0.10

Table 16: Seed-level mean and standard deviation for the C2-1 citation-abstention probe. Values are percentages except average citations. Each model is evaluated on five seeds.

makes non-citation acceptable *when the model is unsure*. The three collapsing models have weak statutory recall (C3: 4–8%; §4.1), so once abstention is permitted, most of their citation activity falls away. Qwen has substantially higher recall (C3: 39.0%), and retains citation at a much higher rate: where the model has statutory knowledge to anchor a citation, a permissive abstention option does not remove it. The probe therefore does not merely suppress citation form; it *separates* ungrounded authority marking, which a single permissive instruction removes, from grounded citation, which persists. Qwen marks the boundary of this effect rather than contradicting it.

The behavior is displaced, not removed. In the three collapsing models, the instruction suppresses the *verifiable* citation marker but not authority-marking behavior itself. Among C2-1 responses that no longer cite an article number, 85.7% still invoke legal authority in non-citational form (e.g., “under the Civil Code,” “per the relevant provisions”). The model does not stop reasoning with legal authority; it stops producing the part of that authority that can be checked. We observed no explicit abstention statements (e.g., “I am unsure of the exact article”) in any of the four models: the shift in citation behavior is silent.

Interpretation. Because the intervention moves the citation process while leaving answer accuracy

essentially intact, it provides prompt-level interventional evidence that answer generation and citation generation are separable. It does not explain the internal mechanism of either process; it shows that the two can be moved independently, and that what a permissive instruction removes is specifically the ungrounded portion of authority marking.